

Class-Aware Hybrid Ensemble for Query-by-Vocal Imitation

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ABSTRACT

We present a Query-by-Vocal Imitation (QBV) system that ensembles four pretrained audio encoders (MobileNetV3, PANNs, PaSST, BEATs), each contrastively fine-tuned on VimSketch pairs [6]. Two inference fusions are compared: **System 1**, a novel *class-aware* mixture-of-experts using per-class Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) [9] for soft weights; and **System 2**, *global* fusion (weighted average) without class information. System 1 attains the best MRR (0.3191) and class-wise metrics, outperforming System 2 and single-model baselines. Code is available at: <https://github.com/RP335/qvim-challenge-aalto>

1 Introduction

Query-by-Vocal Imitation (QBV) involves predicting a reference audio file from a vocal imitation of it, circumventing the need for precise text metadata. The QVIM challenge [1] has highlighted the difficulties of this task in which human vocal imitations exhibit wide timbral variation, class distributions are often imbalanced, and mapping between vocal renditions and diverse sound classes requires robust representations [3]. In our evaluations, we report Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) [9], a metric that reflects the average of the reciprocal ranks of the first correct result. Recent dual-encoder CNNs such as MobileNetV3 [4], with contrastive losses, improved MRR scores. However, single-encoder models still struggle across heterogeneous sound categories [3]. We hypothesize that ensembling diverse encoders, combined with *class-specific fusion* or *global fusion methods* (*weighted average*), can better accommodate the varied acoustic characteristics and differences across classes inherent in the QVIM task.

2 Methods

2.1 Encoders & Training

We fine-tune four AudioSet-pretrained encoders: MobileNetV3 [4], PANNs [7], PaSST [8], and BEATs [2] using InfoNCE [10] to align vocal-imitation and target-sound embeddings in a dual-encoder setup on VimSketch Pairs. For MobileNet, we apply pitch shift, Gaussian noise, and spectrogram mixing [11] augmentations.

2.2 Fusion at Inference

System 1 (Class-Aware). For each class c , we compute per-class validation MRRs for all encoders and, at inference, set

$$w_{i,c} = \frac{\exp(\text{MRR}_{i,c}/T)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \exp(\text{MRR}_{j,c}/T)}, \quad (1)$$

with $T=0.05$ (empirically selected) controlling the sharpness of the softmax across the encoders. If the top MRR exceeds the runner-up by ≥ 0.03 (empirically chosen), we select that encoder; otherwise, we apply the softmax-weighted fusion.

System 2 (Global). Without using class information, we apply simple score averaging with global fusion weights:

$$S_{\text{final}} = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i S_i, \quad (2)$$

where S_i denotes the retrieval score from encoder i , and w_i is its corresponding global fusion weight, with $\sum_{i=1}^N w_i = 1$.

The weights are empirically defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} & (w_{\text{MNetV3}}, w_{\text{BEATs}}, w_{\text{PaSST}}, w_{\text{PANNs}}) \\ & = (0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

3 Results

We evaluate on the DEV dataset [1], reporting Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR), class-wise MRR (c-MRR), and class-wise Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (c-NDCG). Table 1 summarizes retrieval performance.

System 1 yields a 5.5% absolute MRR improvement over the best global fusion and, in a MUSHRA [5] listening evaluation for the QVIM challenge, achieved a subjective MRR of 0.382 and a Mean Opinion Score of 54.7.

Fig. 1: System overview

Table 1: Retrieval performance (higher is better).

Model	MRR	c-MRR	c-NDCG
System 1 (class-aware)	0.3191	0.5564	0.6912
System 2 (global)	0.3026	0.5090	0.6601
MobileNetV3 only	0.2726	0.4683	0.6463

4 Discussion

The class-aware fusion consistently boosts MRR for difficult classes by leveraging encoder specialization. Future work includes optimizing the temperature (T) and dominance threshold hyperparameters in System 1 for improved encoder selection.

5 Summary

We present an ensemble of four contrastively fine-tuned encoders for Query-by-Vocal Imitation. System 1 (class-aware fusion) improves MRR by approximately 17% relative over the best single model.

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